

Co-thinking and Creation for STEAM diversity-gap reduction

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Results of the participation in the STEAM-Labs

GRIAL RESEARCH GROUP (USAL)

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1. Study

The study was divided into two data collections. First, at the beginning of the STEAM-Labs to identify the current situation of the students regarding STEM vocations and the inclusion at the school. On the other hand, at the end of the STEAM-Labs we have collected the same questionnaire to measure the impact in STEM vocations and the perception of the inclusion at the school. However, due to the problems collecting the data at the end of the STEAM-Labs, we have analysed both datasets separately. Moreover, in the final questionnaire, we included questions about the satisfaction with the experience. The results about the satisfaction are described in the quality report.

2. Participants

The study population was Secondary School and High School students from Italy, Turkey, Spain and Germany. Finally, a sample of 503 participants was obtained for the questionnaire applied at the beginning of the STEAM-Labs. The distribution of the questionnaire was implemented in schools by the teachers involved in the STEAM-Labs in each school involved in the Project, both partners and associated partners.

Regarding the participants, 51.89% of the sample were boys and 47.32% were girls, there were also 0.20% of people of other gender. Moreover, we developed the STEAM-Labs in four countries, and we collected 42.35% participants in Italy, 31.61% in Turkey, 23.86% in Spain and 2.19% in Germany. However, not all participants were born in the country in which they studied: 94.04% of the participants live in the country all their life, 3.98% had been in the country for at least 5 years, 0.80% between 2 and 5 years, 0.80% between 6 months and 2 years, and 0.40% had been in the country for less than 6 months. Figure 1 shows in which countries the study participants were born.

Figure 1. Countries in which study participants were born. Source: Own.

The migration level of the sample has therefore been analysed. Figure 2 shows the level of migration of the sample: 85.69% are non-migrants, 9.34% are people with a migrant background (at least one parent born in another country) and 4.97% are migrants.

Figure 2. Migration level. Source: Own.

In relation to parents, Figure 3 shows the map of mother's countries of origin.

Figure 3. Country of birth of mother/tutor. Source: Own.

On the other hand, Figure 4 shows the countries of origin of the father/tutor.

Figure 4. Country of birth of father/tutor. Source: Own.

In relation to the level of education of the caregivers, 57.37% of the mothers/tutors had university studies, 22.31% had secondary education studies, 3.87% had primary education studies and 3.57% had no studies. Similar figures for fathers/tutors, 52.59% of fathers had

university studies, 26.30% had secondary education studies, 3.79% had primary education studies and 2.59% had no studies.

On the other hand, Figure 5 shows the schools participating in the study with the highest representation in the sample.

Figure 5. Schools involved in the STEAM-Labs. Source: Own.

Also, Figure 6 depicts the years in which the participants were born.

Figure 6. Year of birth of participants. Source: Own.

Finally, 64.61% of the participants had not previously participated in activities similar to those developed in the study, the STEAM-Labs; and of the 35.39% had participated in activities related to STE(A)M. Those who participated, answered a question about the satisfaction (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Previous participation in similar activities. Source: Own.

Finally, at the end of the participation in the STEAM-Labs, teachers collected the answers to the final questionnaire. The main problem was that not all the schools collected the final questionnaire. In particular, the students that answered the final questionnaire was 293 people, 124 girls (42.32%), 163 boys (55.63%) and 6 other options (2.05%). 141 participants were from Turkey (48.12%), 98 from Italy (33.45%), 46 from Spain (15.7%),

and 8 from Germany (2.7%). As for the schools, they are the same as in the first questionnaire.

3. Results

The results obtained at the start of the STEAM-Labs are described below. The identification of the items is described in the questionnaire published at <https://zenodo.org/record/7938072>.

The first part of the questionnaire is focused on vocational motivation and perception in STEM to assess the change in perception and self-perception regarding STEM areas, after the application of the didactic units of the project. Table 1 shows the descriptive statistics for measuring the perception of the students regarding STEM studies.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics for the ordinal items in part I of the first block of the questionnaire before starting the STEAM-Labs. Source: Own.

	Valid	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Q014SQ001	503	2.322	1.269	1.000	5.000
Q014SQ002	503	2.304	1.250	1.000	5.000
Q014SQ003	503	2.326	1.201	1.000	5.000
Q014SQ004	503	3.871	1.253	1.000	5.000
Q014SQ005	503	3.897	1.220	1.000	5.000
Q015SQ001	503	2.841	1.350	1.000	5.000
Q015SQ002	503	2.720	1.316	1.000	5.000
Q015SQ003	503	2.847	1.385	1.000	5.000
Q015SQ004	503	3.622	1.387	1.000	5.000
Q015SQ005	503	3.250	1.409	1.000	5.000
Q016SQ001	502	2.528	1.272	1.000	5.000
Q016SQ002	502	2.446	1.343	1.000	5.000
Q016SQ003	502	2.590	1.291	1.000	5.000
Q016SQ004	502	3.518	1.284	1.000	5.000
Q016SQ005	502	3.614	1.300	1.000	5.000

Q017SQ001	503	2.364	1.294	1.000	5.000
Q017SQ002	503	2.197	1.290	1.000	5.000
Q017SQ003	503	2.408	1.279	1.000	5.000
Q017SQ004	503	3.777	1.251	1.000	5.000
Q017SQ005	503	3.797	1.248	1.000	5.000
Q018SQ001	502	2.408	1.300	1.000	5.000
Q018SQ002	502	2.365	1.320	1.000	5.000
Q018SQ003	502	2.470	1.331	1.000	5.000
Q018SQ004	502	3.912	1.279	1.000	5.000
Q018SQ005	502	3.751	1.336	1.000	5.000

We also collected the perception through items of the “Student Attitudes toward STEM Survey-Middle and High School Students”. Table 2 shows the attitudes of the students toward STEM.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics for the ordinal items in part II of the first block of the questionnaire before starting the STEAM-Labs. Source: Own.

	Valid	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Q019SQ001	503	3.306	1.236	1.000	5.000
Q019SQ002	503	3.563	1.164	1.000	5.000
Q019SQ003	503	3.583	1.188	1.000	5.000
Q019SQ004	502	3.363	1.251	1.000	5.000
Q019SQ005	503	3.610	1.120	1.000	5.000
Q019SQ006	503	3.821	1.000	1.000	5.000
Q019SQ007	503	3.380	1.126	1.000	5.000
Q019SQ008	503	3.479	1.196	1.000	5.000

Finally, the questionnaire collected information about the school climate and inclusive space in the school and with peers and teachers using items from the “Survey on Inclusive Education in ten Primary Schools of Kosovo”.

Table 3. Descriptive statistics for the ordinal items in the second block of the questionnaire before starting the STEAM-Labs. Source: Own.

	Valid	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Q020SQ001	498	4.474	0.937	1.000	6.000
Q020SQ002	498	4.476	0.886	1.000	6.000
Q020SQ003	497	4.447	0.848	1.000	6.000
Q020SQ004	497	3.801	1.305	1.000	6.000
Q020SQ005	498	3.835	1.175	1.000	6.000
Q020SQ006	498	4.217	1.053	1.000	6.000
Q020SQ007	498	3.837	1.655	1.000	6.000
Q020SQ008	498	4.504	1.128	1.000	6.000
Q020SQ009	498	4.424	1.149	1.000	6.000
Q020SQ010	498	2.855	1.820	1.000	6.000
Q020SQ011	498	4.171	1.086	1.000	6.000